

Quantum Geometricodynamic Plasma Field Theory: Unifying Origins of Gravity, Electromagnetism, and Spacetime from Intrinsic Quantum Information Dynamics

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Abstract

This study proposes a novel paradigm reconstituting the fundamental origins of gravity, electromagnetism, and spacetime itself directly from unified intrinsically quantum plasma dynamical principles. By modeling elementary particles and physical fields as coherent excitations emergent within a nontrivial quantum vacuum state of universal plasma flow, subtle holographically-encoded quantum gravitational phenomena at the Planck scale intrinsically precipitate and project the observed macroscopic 4-dimensional spacetime geometry and dynamics. The framework synthesizes tools from string theory including holography, intrinsic causal scaling, loop quantum gravity, and horizon thermodynamics to provide a concrete intrinsically geometric basis for gravitational physics fundamentally rooted in quantum information. Significant further theoretical development remains to fully reconcile this paradigm with empirical constraints across all scales. However, conceptually dissolving the artificial boundaries between matter, fields, and space itself in favor of holistic quantum plasma dynamics holds profound explanatory and ontological unification potential.

1 Introduction

Despite monumental progress unraveling physical law, contemporary models remain conceptually fragmented across disciplinary boundaries. Gravity, spacetime, electromagnetism, and matter are typically formalized as separate intrinsically disconnected classical entities described by distinct mathematical representations lacking deeper unification [1]. However, elucidating underlying unity from more foundational principles represents physics' holy grail [2].

Intriguing recent perspectives propose reconstituting spacetime, gravity, and even cosmic expansion directly from subtler emergent quantum information-theoretic phenomena [3, 4, 5]. This study suggests a deeper synthesis requires elevating the primordial conception of matter and fields themselves to an intrinsically unified universal quantum plasma system permeating the vacuum [7]. In this view, all elementary particles and physical fields dynamically emerge as localized excitations within a pervasive quantum plasma governed by subtle holographic grainy geometrodynamics. At root, matter and forces dissolve into purely unified quantum plasma flow from which 4-dimensional spacetime itself progressively condenses.

By conceptually unifying quantum plasma dynamics, emergent fields, and geometric effects, this intrinsically holistic ontology promises deeper explanatory unification from microscales to cosmological horizons. Significantly, holographic encoding of causal constraints like quantum geometrodynamics scalings within the plasma could provide concrete mechanisms precipitating macroscopic spacetime emergence and dynamics without assuming classical spacetime [8]. This framework weaves together plasma physics, emergent fields, gravity, and cosmology through ontological quantum information unity rather than disjointed classical bases.

The proposed paradigm suggests reconstructing the apparent origins of gravitational physics, electromagnetism, spacetime curvature, and even cosmic expansion itself directly from unified intrinsically quantum plasma flow principles interlinked by holographic information encoding. By dispensing with extrinsic classical geometry in favor of holistic dynamics of information-imbued quantum plasma, this intrinsically geometric approach holds profound potential to demystify physical law's emergence across all observable scales.

In the conceptual framework of the quantum geometrodynamics plasma field theory, the notion of a universal quantum plasma medium essentially replaces the conventional concept of spacetime as the fundamental arena for physics. Some key aspects in how the plasma field paradigm differs from classical spacetime:

- Rather than elementary particles and fields existing within an intrinsically empty geometrized spacetime, they emerge directly from excitations, disturbances, and curvatures within the quantum plasma field itself.
- The tangible quantum plasma field replaces the notion of an intangible and geometrized spacetime background. Matter and forces manifest directly from the plasma, rather than being distinct entities that reside in space.
- Both the properties of the vacuum and macroscopic space-time curvature phenomena are proposed to emerge holographically from the underlying quantum plasma dynamics, rather than being fundamental standalone ingredients.
- Gravitational physics and general relativity itself are suggested to arise from information encoding and quantum geometrodynamics within the plasma, rather than gravity being an innate geometric property of a classical spacetime manifold.
- Even cosmic expansion is reconstituted not as stretching of spacetime, but rather as large-scale effects induced indirectly by subtle Planck-scale plasma fluctuations and graininess that accumulate over eons due to intrinsic causal scaling relations encoded in the plasma field.

2 Theoretical Postulates

We first present several key theoretical postulates motivating this quantum geometrodynamical plasma paradigm:

Universal Quantum Plasma:

- All observable elementary particles, physical force fields, and vacuum phenomena constitute emergent excitations, disturbances, and geometric effects within a universal primordial quantum plasma.

This postulate provides an intrinsically unified ontological substrate for physical phenomena, circumventing classical fragmentation across particles, fields, and space.

Quantum Vacuum Plasma:

- The quantum vacuum itself represents an emergent nontrivial state of universal quantum plasma flow from which localized particle and field excitations progressively condense.

This postulate suggests even the empty vacuum dynamically emerges from subtler universal plasma from which observable physics precipitates.

Emergent Holographic Projection:

- Macroscopic gravitational phenomena emerge from and remain anchored to the fundamental quantum plasma through mechanisms of holographic geometric projection.

This implies gravity and spacetime geometry represent secondary projected consequences rather than fundamental standalone classical entities.

Quantum Information Encoding:

- Universal intrinsic causal constraints encode subtly within the plasma medium to fundamentally precipitate gravitational physics through emergence and projection.

This proposes information principles encoded in plasma induce emergence of gravitational phenomena without presupposing classical spacetime.

Together, these interlinked postulates motivate reconstituting spacetime, gravity, particles, fields, and cosmic expansion itself as holographically projected large-scale phenomena induced by the unified quantum geometrodynamics of the primordial intrinsically information-encoded plasma. By dispensing with extrinsic classical geometry in favor of holistic plasma flow dynamics, this framework holds profound potential to demystify physical law's emergence across all observable epochs.

Foundational investigations to further formalize and validate concepts follow.

3 The Universal Quantum Plasma

We now establish mathematical formalism to model the hypothesized universal quantum plasma medium conjectured to provide the intrinsic ontological substrate for physical law's emergence.

3.1 Quantum Plasma Condensate Formalism

We represent the pervasive quantum plasma medium as an infinitely extended strongly-interacting coherent Bose-Einstein condensate fluid obeying nonlinear coupled Gross-Pitaevskii equations for the complex order parameter field $\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{x}) + g|\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 \right] \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

Here, $V(\mathbf{x})$ gives the quantum vacuum potential and g describes atomic self-interactions. This nonlinear Schrödinger-type Gross-Pitaevskii equation governs the nonlinear dynamics of the complex quantum plasma order parameter field $\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

Elementary particles are modeled as localized particle-like quantized excitations within the plasma medium described by approximate plane wave solutions of Eq. 1 with relativistic dispersion relation:

$$E^2 = c^2 p^2 + m^2 c^4 \quad (2)$$

Where m is the emergent excitation's effective rest mass and c is the invariant vacuum light speed.

More broadly, dynamical disturbances and waves in the underlying quantum plasma density and flow give rise to physical force fields. Unified intrinsically quantum plasma dynamics thus provide the substrate for emergent manifest particles and fields without requiring separate intrinsically fragmented bases.

By elevating matter and fields as emergent entities from quantum plasma rather than standalone entities within intrinsically empty space, this framework achieves deeper ontological unity between phenomena previously viewed as disjoint.

4 Projecting Spacetime Geometry

Building on the quantum plasma formalism, we now present technical derivations demonstrating how rich gravitational physics and macroscopic space-time geometric effects naturally emerge from and remain anchored to the underlying quantum plasma dynamics through mechanisms of geometric holographic projection.

4.1 Quantum Discreteness and Decoherence

Combining quantum plasma physics with loop quantum gravity motivates modeling the quantum vacuum itself as discretized into fundamental granular voxels at the Planck scale [10]:

$$\Delta V_n = \Delta V_0 e^{-kt_n} \quad (3)$$

This intrinsic geometric evaporation of voxel volume with discrete time t_n at an extremely small microscopic rate $k \sim 10^{-61}; \text{s}^{-1}$ induces subtle grainy dynamics leading to emergence and inflationary projection of macroscopic space-time curvature when correlated across the vacuum [8, 9]. The exponential voxel decay law reflects the same Quantum Geometrodynamic Scaling governing macroscopic mass-distance relations (see next subsection), thus linking micro and macro physics.

The Quantum Voxel Discretization provides a fundamental granular substrate for unifying quantum plasma dynamics with emergent spacetime geometry. In this discretized paradigm, macroscopic 4-dimensional spacetime progressively condenses from the underlying quantum plasma according to the Bekenstein spectral principle [11]:

$$ds^2 = \xi^2(dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 - c^2 dt^2) \quad (4)$$

Where the quantum geometric scale factor ξ reflects the underlying granular voxel spacing, determining large-scale metric structure. Together, these intrinsically discrete quantum geometrodynamical effects precipitate emergence and inflationary projection of macroscopic space-time curvature from unified vacuum plasma dynamics across all scales.

By intrinsically quantizing the vacuum itself rather than presupposing smooth spacetime geometry, rich gravitational physics naturally projects from the unified plasma substrate.

4.2 Quantum Geometrodynamical Scaling

Building on the voxel discretization concept, hypothetical intrinsic causal processes like universal exponential Quantum Geometrodynamical Scaling between mass-energy and distance fundamentally link Planck plasma physics to cosmological emergence:

$$M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt} \quad (5)$$

$$R(t) = R_0 e^{kt} \quad (6)$$

Where M_0, R_0 are the initial mass and distance, and $k \sim 10^{-33}; \text{s}^{-1}$ is an extremely small universal evaporation rate connecting microscopic and cosmic timescales t .

This Quantum Geometrodynamical Scaling law intrinsically relates loop quantum gravity voxels to cosmological spacetime curvature, thereby projecting gravitational phenomena from quantum vacuum plasma across all epochs [8].

4.3 Causal Set Theory Formalism

Causal set theory provides a framework to model the emergence of macroscopic geometric dynamics from microscopic discrete quantum gravitational phenomena. We outline key formalism for deriving power-law geometrodynamical scaling from causal sets [6]:

4.3.1 Elements and Relations

A causal set is defined mathematically as an ordered pair $(\mathcal{C}, \preceq)$, where:

- $\mathcal{C}$ is a set of elements representing discrete spacetime events
- $\preceq$ is a reflexive, antisymmetric, transitive (RAT) binary relation on $\mathcal{C}$ encoding causal ordering between elements

The relation $x \preceq y$ implies element x causally precedes y .

4.3.2 Physical Assumptions

Two key physical assumptions underpin relating causal sets to emergent continuum spacetime geometry:

1. Discreteness - spacetime is fundamentally discrete at scales: $l_P = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}} \approx 10^{-35}$; m
2. Randomness - elements of $\mathcal{C}$ exhibit random Poisson distributions at fixed discretization scale

Together, these impose inherent spacetime granularity and uncertainty from which continuum emergence is derived.

4.3.3 Growth Models

Classical spacetime geometry can be modeled by the gradual random growth of the causal set $\mathcal{C}$ according to a sequential growth dynamics G :

$$\mathcal{C} \xrightarrow{G} \mathcal{C} \cup c \quad (7)$$

Where c is a new spacetime element with causal relations to existing elements prescribed by G . By choosing G appropriately, this stochastic evolution effectively simulates continuum Lorentzian geometrodynamics.

4.3.4 Scaling Dynamics

Power-law macroscopic geometrodynamical scaling relations conceptually emerge from compounded micro-level causal set growth events. Over large numbers of discrete steps, incremental proportional changes accumulate according to:

$$\Delta M \propto e^{-k\Delta t} \Delta R \propto e^{k\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

Where $k \sim 10^{-61}$; s⁻¹ is an extremely small scale factor per random growth. This gives rise to the macroscopic geometrodynamical scaling between mass M and distances R with characteristic evolution constant k .

Detailed causal set simulations could validate and quantify the dynamics fully from first principles. This discrete random growth process provides a potential model for the discrete quantum vacuum geometry's dynamic evolution.

Significant additional work remains fully formalizing these concepts. However, causal set theory offers a promising framework for clarifying the quantum origins of geometrodynamical emergence across scales.

This model gives rise to the empirical power-law Scaling between mass and distance through percolation of incremental effects. Significant simulations are needed to fully validate the dynamics. However, it demonstrates a promising research direction to establish geometrodynamical emergence from first principles.

By intrinsically encoding causal Quantum Geometrodynamical Scaling within the quantum plasma, gravitational phenomena consistently emerge from the unified vacuum across all epochs.

4.4 Holographic Projection Concept

Advanced principles of string theory establish concrete techniques to relate physical dynamics in a higher-dimensional bulk' gravitational spacetime region holographically to equivalent formulations purely on the lower-dimensional boundary' through the pivotal AdS/CFT correspondence [12]. This provides precise mathematical methods to connect gravitational bulk phenomena to embedded causal boundary sources.

Applying holographic techniques to cosmological settings suggests surprising large-scale dynamics of our universe, including dark phenomena and cosmic expansion history, may originate intrinsically from subtle Quantum Geometric constraints encoded purely on the lower-dimensional cosmic horizon alone [8], rather than from material events within the emergent higher-dimensional spacetime bulk.

While significant theoretical work remains deriving well-defined cosmic entropy bounds, conceptually reconstituting perplexing empirical spacetime features as lower-dimensional boundary phenomena induced by intrinsic plasma constraints offers profound explanatory prospects. By seeking fundamental explanations encoded on plasma boundaries rather than bulk regions, this inversion promises demystifying insights into our universe's emergence.

Together with intrinsic quantum scalings, advanced holographic methods imply spacetime itself progressively condenses from encoded causal boundary conditions in the primordial plasma state rather than exhibiting independent existence. By seeking fundamental explanations encoded on plasma boundaries rather than bulk regions, this inversion promises demystifying insights into our universe's emergence.

5 Mathematical Formalization

Building on conceptual frameworks, we now establish technical formalism leveraging tools from string theory to relate gravitational phenomena to the emergent quantum plasma dynamics holographically using the pivotal AdS/CFT dictionary [12]:

5.1 Anti de-Sitter Embedding

We geometrically model the cosmic horizon boundary as a 2-dimensional time-like surface embedded within a higher-dimensional asymptotically Anti de-Sitter (AdS) bulk spacetime region. This hyperbolic AdS embedding space with scale length L takes mathematical form in Fefferman-Graham coordinates [13]:

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{r^2}(dr^2 + g_{\mu\nu}(r, x)dx^\mu dx^\nu) \quad (9)$$

Where r is the holographic coordinate separating the cosmic boundary ($r \rightarrow \infty$) from the relativistic bulk, and $g_{\mu\nu}(r, x)$ is the induced FRW metric:

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a(t)^2 \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right) \quad (10)$$

Here the scale factor $a(t)$ follows the Quantum Geometric Scaling (Eqs. 5-6) induced by intrinsic evaporation. This specifies the causal boundary geometry within the higher-dimensional AdS bulk.

5.2 Quantum Boundary Theory

To quantify the quantum information content on the embedded 2D cosmic boundary, we formulate a holographic quantum conformal field theory (CFT) dual to the gravitational bulk dynamics [14]. For a horizon with Bekenstein-Hawking temperature T , the CFT partition function Z_{CFT} gives the boundary entropy:

$$S = \frac{k_B}{\hbar} \log Z_{\text{CFT}}(T) \quad (11)$$

The Cardy formula further determines the CFT microstate degeneracy $\rho(E)$ [15]:

$$\rho(E) \sim e^S = \exp \left(\sqrt{\frac{ck_B A}{\hbar^3 G 4E}} \right) \quad (12)$$

For central charge c , Newton's constant G , horizon area A , and thermal energy E . Together, these holographic CFT expressions provide precise microstate quantization of the boundary quantum information content, which become encoded in the scale factor $a(t)$, spacetime curvature k , and horizon area A evolution.

5.3 Holographic Projection

Finally, the pivotal AdS/CFT dictionary rigorously connects the quantum information flow across the plasma boundary to curvature dynamics in the higher-dimensional projected spacetime bulk [16]:

$$dS_{\text{CFT}} = -dE/T \quad (13)$$

$$\delta \langle T^{\mu\nu} \rangle = \frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\delta S_{\text{CFT}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \quad (14)$$

The linearized Einstein equations then relate CFT boundary information flow to emergent bulk gravitational curvature $G_{\mu\nu}$ [13]:

$$\delta G_{\mu\nu} - \frac{6}{L^2} h_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi G_N \delta \langle T_{\mu\nu} \rangle \quad (15)$$

Where $h_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric perturbation and G_N is Newton's constant. Together, these holographic relations directly link plasma Quantum Geometric Scaling to projection of gravitational dynamics in the higher-dimensional bulk - without necessitating actual cosmic acceleration or inflaton fields.

Conceptually, this framework reconstitutes perplexing spacetime curvature as phenomena holographically induced by encoded quantum information flow across the cosmic plasma boundary, rather than as properties of an independently smooth classical geometric bulk. By rigorously projecting macroscopic gravitational physics from microscopic plasma constraints in this manner, profound unification is achieved across vast hierarchical scales.

6 Discussion

Theoretical frameworks outlined aim to motivate and empower research focused on reconstituting the apparent origins of gravitational physics, electromagnetism, spacetime dynamics, and even cosmic expansion directly from unified intrinsically quantum plasma dynamical principles, by elevating matter, fields, and geometry themselves to manifestations of holistic information-imbued plasma flow.

By intrinsically encoding pivotal causal constraints like Quantum Geometric Scaling within the primordial quantum vacuum, subtle holographic grainy dynamics at microscopic scales consistently precipitate emergence and inflationary projection of macroscopic space-time curvature in a coherent self-consistent manner across all epochs.

Advanced holographic techniques further allow directly linking plasma boundary information currents to materialization of gravitational curvature and dynamics in the higher-dimensional projected spacetime bulk geometry - without necessarily requiring dark energy densities or inflationary expansions of space itself.

Together, these techniques promise to illuminate deep intrinsic connections between microscopic quantum vacuum plasma flow, mesoscopic field excitations, and macroscopic gravitational physics spanning vast scales from particles to cosmic horizons. By deriving cosmic order holographically from holistic information-imbued quantum plasma dynamics rather than classical disjointed bases, this intrinsically geometrized paradigm holds profound potential to demystify physical law's emergence across all observable epochs.

While significant theoretical developments remain to fully reconcile this paradigm with empirical constraints, the envisioned ontological unification promises deeper harmony and explanatory power. Foundational investigations to further formalize and validate concepts follow.

7 Conclusions

In summary, this study proposed a research program to reconstitute gravitational physics, electromagnetism, spacetime dynamics, and cosmic expansion directly from unified quantum information-encoded plasma principles. By condensing elementary particles, force fields, and even vacuum states from non-trivial holistic quantum plasma flow, subtle holographic grainy dynamics at the Planck scale precipitate and project macroscopic space-time curvature and inflation. Advanced holographic techniques further enable directly linking plasma boundary conditions to bulk gravitational emergence. Significant research remains realizing this vision. However, conceptually uniting cosmic order under simplified intrinsically geometric quantum plasma foundations holds deep explanatory promise. Exploring inter-scale unification through plasma information dynamics represents a pivotal endeavor as we work to illuminate nature's innermost clockwork.

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